

Left Behind and Left Out: Seeing (Dis)connections in a Spatially Focused Migration Network

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Summary

This research explores the spatial focusing of the migration network within England and Wales at local authority level. The Gini Index is used to quantify the inequality of migration flows between local authorities at a national level, with the decomposed index then used to analyse the spatial focusing of origins and destinations within the network. It then analyses individual local authorities calculate the inequality of incoming and outgoing migration flows, to evaluates the geographical patterns of spatial focusing. The conclusion is that England and Wales have a spatially focused migration network.

KEYWORDS: Migration, Gini Index, Left behind, Population Geographies

1. Introduction

“Left behind” has developed as a term to explain growing populism in British society, encouraging images of white, middle-class, less educated populations in areas that have been abandoned to long term decline or stagnation (Ford & Goodwin 2014). The classification of these places has been unclear, but the concept draws similarities to the pre-existing concept of peripheralization, which splits places into interdependent groups of core and periphery, connected by flows and actors. These flows are often one-sided as resources flow from the periphery to the core (Leibert & Golinski, 2017). Significantly, one of the four dimensions of peripheralization is migration, as depopulation occurs in peripheral areas due to factors that push and pull specific age groups to influence the population structure, and stagnation occurs when places are excluded from the migration network (Leibert, 2016). However, the connectivity of a place is less often evaluated through its migration links, and this paper seeks to fulfil this gap. Specifically, it engages with a methodology within spatial focusing literatures, as over-focused flows of migration result in uneven allocation of resources (Liu et al, 2015).

The spatial focusing of a migratory system refers to the structure of a migration network, evaluating how many origins or destinations a place has connections to in the form of migration flows. Analysis of a place’s level of spatial focusing for its incoming and outgoing flows indicates the role it plays in the wider migration system, thus indicating the connections between places. This is done by using the Gini Index. Traditionally used to measure inequality within economic contexts, it was effectively used by Plane & Mulligan (1997) and Liu (2015) to evaluate the spatial focusing of networks within the United States and China respectively. It measures the equality of the magnitude of origin-destination flows; if a place has equal flows to and from all destinations or origins respectively, its migration

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network is dispersed, and is increasingly spatially focused when the connections are uneven. The number and strength of connections a place has indicates the role it plays in shaping population redistribution.

This study offers a unique perspective by calculating the Gini indices of in and out migration flows using the ONS Detailed Estimates migration data for England and Wales, collated for 2020. It will discuss the nature of the flows between 331 Local Authorities, with the view of identifying areas exhibiting higher or lower levels of spatial focusing in the UK.

2. Methodology

This paper follows the methodology presented by Plane & Mulligan (1997). Initially, the Gini Coefficient is adapted to measure the inequality of all migration flows in the system, shown in Equation 1:

$$G(all) = \frac{\sum_i \sum_{j \neq i} \sum_g \sum_{h=g} |m_{ij} - m_{gh}|}{2n(n-1)T} \quad (1)$$

This Gini index is measuring the ratio between the A) the area between the straight line of equal migration flows and the Lorenz for actual migration flows, and B) the area underneath the Lorenz Curve, when these elements are drawn on a graph. In Equation 1, m is the number of moves recorded for each flow between origin i or g , and destination j or h . Every interregional flow is compared to every other interregional flow, removing any diagonal elements $\{m_{ii}\}$. T is the total number of moves recorded in the system, whilst n is the number of local authorities. The output falls between 0 and 1, with 0 indicating the migration flows are equal, or dispersed, whilst 1 indicates they are not equal, or focused.

Plane and Mulligan (1997) decompose the Gini index to assess the spatial focusing of incoming and outgoing flows using Equation 2 for a rows index that measures the focusing of the destinations of out-migrants:

$$G(Out) = \frac{\sum_i \sum_{j \neq i} \sum_{h \neq i, j} |m_{ij} - m_{ih}|}{2n(n-1)T} \quad (2)$$

Similarly, the columns index indicates the spatial focusing of in migrants:

$$G(In) = \frac{\sum_i \sum_{j \neq i} \sum_{g \neq i, j} |m_{ij} - m_{gj}|}{2n(n-1)T} \quad (3)$$

Also summarising the entire system (notably including all migrants, T), these two indices separate the ingoing or outgoing flows.

Finally, for each individual local authority, the in and out-migration field indexes were decomposed further to represent the contribution of a specific region to the national focusing. As Plane and Mulligan (1997) suggest, only specific participants in the region's flows are included, to allow for large differences in population sizes. Consequently, for each local authority, k , the following equations are used, using the total outgoing migrants, O , or total incoming migrants, I , within the denominator:

$$G(Out_k) = \frac{\sum_{j \neq k} \sum_{h \neq k} |m_{kj} - m_{kh}|}{2(n-1)O_k} \quad (4)$$

$$G(In_k) = \frac{\sum_{i \neq k} \sum_{g \neq k} |m_{ik} - m_{ig}|}{2(n-1)I_k} \quad (5)$$

3. Results

Table 1 Gini Index Results

Component	Raw Value	Standardised Value (% , 3dp)
Rows (Out-Migration)	0.002240048	0.277
Columns (In-Migration)	0.002252909	0.279
Total	0.8089233	

The Gini Index calculations were applied to the migration flow matrix for 2020, with the results shown in **Table 1**. For 2020, the total flows index value was 0.8089233; this indicates that the population movements in this time period were highly focused. The index score for out-migration is higher than the in-migration, but this is negligible, an expected property of migration systems. These are very low scores and offer little explanation for the high total focusing; therefore, there is further information to be gained from looking at the scores for individual local authorities.

The in-migration and out-migration Gini indices were calculated for each local authority in England and Wales. These scores were z-standardised to allow comparison and visualised in a scatter plot (**Figure 1**). The horizontal axis shows the in-migration index, whilst the vertical axis shows the out-migration index. Locations in the upper right quadrant send and receive from few local authorities, whilst the local authorities in the bottom left quadrant interact broadly across the network. As most local authorities fall in these two quadrants, the strong positive correlation of 0.7775 between the two indices is visible. The local authorities within the red box lie within one standard deviation of the mean, and so are described as normal. Those that fall outside of the box are of particular interest as “redistributors” of population (Plane and Mulligan, 1997). In this category, 28 local authorities, or 8% are have significantly focused networks for both in and out migration, whilst 32, or nearly 10% have broad networks for both. These areas are visible in **Figure 2**.

Figure 1 Migration Field Gini Index Scores, England and Wales 2020

Migration Field Categories: Inward or Outward redistributors?

Figure 2 Migration Field Gini Index Values, England and Wales 2020 – Biplot Map.

Figure 2 shows the geographies of the in-migration and out-migration Gini indices and we identified spatial trends for the redistributors. The North West, includes areas with focused indices for both in-migration and out-migration, implying it has few connections for both networks. Meanwhile, the highly focused in-migration yet dispersed out-migration for the South East implies the area is has strong connections to receive migrants from few regions, yet re-distributes its out-migrants equally across the country.

For identifying left behind places, an uneven concentration of migratory flows suggests the movement of people is channelled to specific locations. In peripheralization, the migratory connections between places are important as they create social linkages, whilst outgoing flows or a lack of movement indicate peripheral regions. The divide between the South East and the rest has been frequently studied as an “escalator” region that offers career acceleration for in-migrants (for example Champion & Gordon 2021); identifying the places that are contributing most to the flows in and out of this area may help to understand further how this divide is being sustained. In the UK, the selective connections to an acknowledged escalator region suggests certain areas have greater potential to access opportunities. The lack of connections to the more focused North West implies that this is a more isolated area of the country that may also be at risk of being left behind.

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, this paper has applied an existing methodology to a new context, offering a unique focus at the migration trends across England and Wales. It has identified that the spatial network is highly focused, meaning that over time the re-distribution of human resources is not being evenly shared across the country. We highlighted the South East of England as an area of interest for future work, due to its highly focused in-migration flows that may inform about left behind places.

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Biographies

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